

Life and work of the People's Artist of Uzbekistan Bahadir Jalolov

MAMATKULOV RASHIDBEK RAVSHANBEKOVICH

Kokan State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of "Fine art and engineering graphics"

ANNOTATION

After the independence of Uzbekistan, the process of restoration of spiritual heritage and realization of national culture in the historical period drew the attention of artists to the recent and distant history of the Motherland, the layer of forgotten values. The President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the decision to establish the Culture and Art Development Fund at the Ministry of Culture. The text of the decision adopted on October 16 was announced by the UzA. The new fund is being established in order to increase the effectiveness of the implementation of state policy in the management system in the field of culture and art.

Key words: Drawing, student, computer, effective lesson, concept, necessity, standard, training, sequence, coherence, didactic demand, New fund, culture, art, historical period, spiritual -heritage, Bahadir Jalolov.

When we say Bahadir of Uzbek fine art, we see an artist who devoted his whole life to colors, who creates by turning imagination into life, life into imagination, who studies nature and man through images, and a great thinker. Being able to reflect life in pieces on a piece of gray fabric, to be able to fit the most important calls, deep thoughts and feelings that have been born in the heart into a network of lines is not essentially a profession or a craft, but it is - in fact, it is a truly divine rank that

cannot be completed by anyone. Such a great title called artistry is the life work of the People's Artist of Uzbekistan Bahadir Jalalov.

Bahadir Jalolov is the People's Artist of Uzbekistan, winner of the State Prize named after Alisher Navoi, one of the talented artists contributing to the development of modern painting art. Bahadir Jalolov was born on May 27, 1948 in Tashkent. In 1968, he graduated from the P. P. Benkov Republican School of Art. In 1974, I.E. He graduated from the Faculty of Monumental Decoration of the St. Petersburg Institute of Painting, Sculpture and Architecture named after Repin. In his youth, he studied with the master of portrait art, Abdulhaq Abdullaev.

In the first samples of the artist's creative activity, national feelings are expressed in different colors. B. Jalalov continued his studies in fine arts and later learned the secrets of fine arts from Chingiz Ahmarov, Rozi Choriyev, Milnikov, Korolyov. That is why the high skill is clearly visible in the portraits created by him. The harmony of emotions in his work makes the audience fall in love with him.

In particular, we see that the composition "Birth of Dance" not only glorifies Uzbek dancers, but also shows sincere respect and love for them. Bahadir Jalolov achieved many achievements in the art of portraiture. The image of the beloved children of the Uzbek people is expressed in his full-fledged works.

In this place, especially, the figure of such great figures as the academic artist Orol Tansikboev, the great scientist, academician Vahid Zohidov, the famous artists of art Kamil Yormatov, Malik Qayumov, Muhyiddin Rahimov, Hamro Rahimova, Akrom Toshkanboev, Damir Roziboev is an example of our word. The artist always strives to study the human personality and feel it in every way.

In fact, as we have seen above, the main scope of Bahadir Jalolov's creative activity is focused on the image of people, i.e. creating portraits. In fine art, he enriches the world of his colors with new colors.

Another aspect of Bahadir Jalolov's maturity is that he is an artist who mastered

Eastern and Western traditions, found the commonality in these traditions and managed to bring them to the surface. That is why it has attracted the attention of art lovers of foreign countries.

The artist decorates luxurious palaces and buildings in advanced countries of the world with his monumental panels. The well-known scientist Tilab Mahmudov evaluated the work of the artist and said: "For Bahadur, the history of man and humanity was a puzzle. He tries to solve this puzzle, to find points of harmony between the history of his people and the history of humanity." In fact, the artist, as a broad-minded creator, strives to learn the secrets of man, the universe, and the universe. Bahadir Jalolov (1948.27.5, Tashkent) is a master of painting, People's Artist of Uzbekistan (1992), Uzbekistan (1997) and Kyrgyzstan (1998), I. Repin Institute of Painting, Sculpture and Architecture graduated (1974). Teacher at Tashkent Institute of Theater and Fine Arts (1974-80); Since 1997, the head of the prestigious painting workshop at the National Institute of Painting and Design, prof. (2000).

Chairman of the board of the Union of Artists of Uzbekistan (1987-92). He started his work by creating portraits. In his portraits, situations that give an idea of people's profession are reflected, the creative work process, deep psychological state are skillfully shown ("Architect", 1972; "Maskharaboz Akrom Yusupov", 1974; "Autoportrait", 1975; "Potter Woman. People" Master Hamro Rahimova, 1977, Memory of Artist Sh. Rahimov, 1980. 70's From the end of the 1980s to the beginning of the 1990s, he has been actively working in the field of artistic painting: his murals on the building of the Karshi Musical Drama Theater, the lobby of the kitchen of the "Chimyon" sanatorium (1981), and the House of Cinematographers in Tashkent (1982) make the artist a sought-after, unique style. introduced as an artist. "Birth of Dance" (1982) for the foyer of the "Bahor" concert hall, for the wall of the Tallimarjon pump station club in the Kashkadarya region (1983), for the foyer

of the Ko'kan Theater 17 (1987), for the school building in Khojand, Tajikistan (1988) , "Kortreik 200" (1990) in Kortrijk, Belgium, murals, landscapes for the Turkestan Palace in Tashkent ("Dreams of Omar Khayyom", 1993) and others ("Spring in Isfarada", "Mountain Village. So' Qmoq", "Old Gurzuf Street", etc.), illustrations created for books (Navoi, T. Tula, U. Nasir)

The artist has been busy with a large and unexpected exhibition project for more than a year. After all, it is not just a retrospective, but reflects the "life path" of the artist, who shows his achievements through various hardships. Despite his old age, Bahadir Jalal is full of enthusiasm for creative research, he started to work with new technologies, moving away from his previous artistic methods. He described the jubilee exhibition project as "... And that's when it all started!" called it. This, in turn, leads to various philosophical observations, thoughts about the role of the artist in the world, and the understanding of secrets and meanings. b.) is the author. Laureate of the State Prize of the Republic of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi. November 13, 2018 at the Gallery of Fine Arts of Uzbekistan The Gallery of Fine Arts of Uzbekistan dedicated to the 70th birthday of the People's Artist of Uzbekistan Bahadir Jalal "..and that's when it all started" presented his personal exhibition. The anniversary exhibition "... and that's when it all started!" and calling for philosophical observations of the artist's position and views in the world, allows to understand the secret and meaning of every artist's beginning of his creative path. "I am not bound by any tradition. The main thing is love and light," the artist admitted. He is always open to the dialogue of Eastern and Western cultures and looks for his personal version in every plastic concept.

Growing up in the model of Eastern and Western arts, the artist not only creates on the basis of modernist forms and colors, but also begins to explore the abstract foundations of ornament based on the experiences of Eastern spirituality, reflects

Truth as an image of absolute perfection in its mathematical precision and geometric perfection. .

In many of Jalal's new works, the composition appears as a systematic formula, with its thin lines reminiscent of the game of "girix" ornament. This geometric grid, which means "knot" in Arabic, brings the idea of connecting and tying everything together, inviting us to continue. But the main thing is not them, but the lines, they are the tone of the infinite eternity, it is it that shows the wholeness in its versatility.

Currently, Jalal continues his research in abstract works inspired by oriental calligraphy. This is an original improvisation of Uzbek master painters and ornamentalists, characteristic of skilled masters. According to Jalal himself, the historical heritage is a kind of chaotic world, a world of love and beauty, which he creates with constant interest in his work. But the main and highest object in the works of the artist is a person. Jalal's new projects contain many cultural expressions and combinations, his appeal to the great European masters and the aesthetics of traditional Uzbek art is equivalent to opening an unexplored world. One can feel that the artist, like his great generations, aspires to heights, to some kind of divinity, to harmony, and is not indifferent to feeling dramatic emotions.

As a real artist, he is not indifferent to the problems of the modern world, and through his new projects, he tries to give his answer to the cruelty and indifference of humanity, the wars and injustices happening in the world. "I consider myself very lucky because I can feel emotions that other people can't. These are not only universal human problems, but also all the beauties of our world: love, kindness, compassion. I am an artist and I feel many events and processes deeply and acutely. I experience all this and it gives me the motivation to create. For me, 2017 was a year of preparation for my personal exhibition and constant creative research.

Also, one of the important events was my personal exhibition in Dubai, which received positive reviews from many art lovers. The book "A line to Eternity"

prepared by the Italian publishing house "Skira" was one of the unique events of the artistic life of Central Asia. I want to convey many ideas to the audience through my upcoming exhibition. All my ideas and thoughts are realized through various unexpected directions and projects of art." Bahadir Jalal says.

In 1987, I studied at the fourth stage of the Kokon Art Academy. A friend and I went to the newly opened theater building in the city after hearing that the people's artist Bahadir Jalolov was working on murals. We went up to the second floor, the builders were busy, things were getting hotter. The chiefs are inspecting the rooms of the building under construction. The theater yard is full of construction materials.

Seating is being installed for the outdoor theater auditorium. My friend watched it for a while and left saying he had work. I said that I couldn't leave without seeing the work of the artists. On the second floor of the building, two artists from Tashkent are painting a large mural about the life and art of Kokan, 7-8 meters high, 30 meters wide and 30 meters long.

REFERENCES

1. Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan - letter J
2. Boymetov B. —Pencil drawing. Textbook Part 1. Tashkent, 2006
3. Abdirasilov S., Tolipov N. —Rangtasvir Tashkent, 2005.
4. Tolipov N., Abdirasilov S., Oripova N. Painting. T., 2006.
5. Abdirasilov S., Tolipov N., Oripova N. —Tabletop painting (part 2). T., 2003.
6. Tojiev B. —The text of lectures on the science of hand-drawn painting. T., 2000.
7. Tolipov N. Abdirasilov S. —Table painting-Tashkent. 2005.
8. Tojiev B. —Learning the basics of pencil drawing. Tashkent 1994.
9. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". A perfect generation is the foundation of Uzbekistan's development. -T.: Sharq, 1997, pp. 20-29.
10. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the National Program of Personnel Training". A perfect generation is the foundation of Uzbekistan's development. -

T.: East, 1997, pp. 31-61.